

KITAABI FOR UZBEK LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract. *Kitaabi is an innovative online platform designed to facilitate the language-learning process, offering live classes and interactive AI-driven feedback mechanisms. It supports seven languages, particularly focusing on the Uzbek language. The lessons and AI-based features are based on the CEFR standards to ensure level-based teaching. This paper explores Kitaabi's architecture, technical components, and educational impact, comparing it with existing platforms. Future developments include gamification elements and expansion of the system's architecture and functionalities to include UzWordnet and other low-resource languages, especially of Central Asia.*

Keywords: *uzbek Language, Learning, Online Education, AI-driven Feedback, Gamification.*

Annotatsiya. *Kitaabi – bu til o‘rganish jarayonini osonlashtirish uchun ishlab chiqilgan innovatsion onlayn platforma bo‘lib, onlayn darslar va interaktiv sun‘iy intellekt asosida tekshirish va baholash mexanizmlarini taqdim etadi. Platforma yetti tilda ishlaydi va ayniqsa, o‘zbek tiliga alohida e‘tibor qaratadi. Darslar va sun‘iy intellektga asoslangan funksiyalar CEFR standartlariga mos ravishda bilim darajalariga muvofiq o‘qitishni ta‘minlaydi. Ushbu maqolada Kitaabi‘ning arxitekturasi, texnik komponentlari va ta‘lim sohasidagi ta‘siri tahlil qilinadi hamda mavjud platformalar bilan solishtiriladi. Kelajakdagi ishlanmalar o‘yinlashtirish elementlarini hamda tizim arxitekturasi va funksiyalarini UzWordnet va boshqa kam resursli tillarni, xususan, Markaziy Osiyoning boshqa tillarini qamrab olish uchun kengaytirishni o‘z ichiga oladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *o‘zbek tili, Til o‘rganish, Onlayn ta‘lim, Sun‘iy intellekt asosida fikr-mulohaza, O‘yinlashtirish.*

Аннотация. *Kitaabi — это инновационная онлайн-платформа, созданная для упрощения процесса изучения языков, предлагающая занятия и интерактивные механизмы на основе искусственного интеллекта. Она поддерживает семь языков, уделяя особое внимание узбекскому языку. Уроки и функции на базе ИИ соответствуют стандартам CEFR, обеспечивая обучение по уровням. В данной статье рассматривается архитектура, технические компоненты и образовательное влияние Kitaabi, а также проводится сравнение с существующими платформами. Будущие разработки включают элементы геймификации и расширение архитектуры и функциональности системы для включения UzWordnet и других малоресурсных языков, особенно стран Центральной Азии.*

Ключевые слова: *узбекский язык, Изучение языков, Онлайн-образование, Проверка с помощью ИИ, Геймификация.*

1 Introduction

There is no doubt that the languages are at the core of human perception. We perceive the world through the languages we possess: the information shared or received every day, the knowledge gained, and the whole world that surrounds us manifest themselves through

certain languages. They have also been the primary tool for communication in human history. From the earliest times until now languages have helped people express their thoughts, and ideas, and communicate with each other. The early traditional formats of language learning have been replaced with new learning strategies [1]. The dramatic technological advancements made it possible to access tremendous amounts of data with a few clicks enforcing individual self-education [2].

1.1 Overview of Kitaabi

Kitaabi¹ is an online platform aimed at connecting learners with fluent language teachers for mastering foreign languages. Launched in 2023, Kitaabi is designed as a web application with a complementary mobile application ready for deployment. Developed by Mirkamol Mirkamilov and Saydobid Khusanov, the platform caters to a global audience with a focus on usability and accessibility.

Currently, Kitaabi supports seven languages: Uzbek, English, French, Italian, German, Spanish, and Chinese. Lessons are facilitated by volunteer language experts, and the user base includes over 170 members from countries such as the US, Canada, and Europe. The platform has grown organically through word-of-mouth, with advertising campaigns planned for the near future.

1.2 Features

- **Interactive Lessons:** Live sessions hosted by experienced volunteers.
- **AI Help:** A feature that provides users with real-time feedback on their text input in supported languages. The system evaluates text for CEFR levels, offers corrections, and suggests improvements.
- **Mobile Compatibility:** A mobile application is fully developed and ready for release.

Figure 1: Class Dashboard.

¹ <https://kitaabi.academy/>

Figure 2: Individual Class View.

1.3 User Statistics and Engagement

As of January 2025:

- **Total Users:** more than 170
- **Active Languages:** 7
- **Demographics:** Users from **46 countries**, with a strong presence in the United States, Uzbekistan, Canada, Germany, India, and Slovakia, highlighting global demand.
- **Growth Strategy:** Organic growth through referrals, with planned marketing initiatives.

1.4 Mobile Version and API Development

In 2024, we developed a *mobile version* of Kitaabi to provide a seamless language learning experience on smartphones and tablets. This version retains all the core features of the web platform while offering a more user-friendly and accessible interface for learners on the go.

• **Cross-Platform Availability:** The mobile app is available for both Android and iOS users, ensuring a wider reach.

• **Releasing an API for Language Learning:** To enhance integration capabilities, we have developed and released a RESTful API that allows third-party applications and educational platforms to leverage Kitaabi's language learning resources. This API provides structured access to lessons, vocabulary data, and AI-driven assessments.

• **Optimized User Experience:** The interface has been specifically designed for smaller screens, allowing users to engage in lessons, exercises, and AI-driven assessments efficiently.

• **AI Chatbot Integration:** Just like the web version, the mobile app features an AI-driven chatbot that evaluates users' writing skills based on the CEFR framework.

• **Gamification Features:** The upcoming updates will introduce interactive elements such as badges, leaderboards, and language challenges to make learning more engaging.

• **Offline Mode (Planned):** We are working on an offline mode that will allow users to access lessons and practice without an internet connection.

Figure 3: Main Page (Explore and AI Help).

2 Related Work

Similar language-learning applications include Duolingo, the famous gamified learning platform that provides learners with a fun approach to learning. Analysing the history, it can be seen that the platform had many reformations in terms of interface structure, learning curriculum, and more. However, one of the key aspects of the application that stayed the same was how a lesson was organized, not considering minor modifications. The same questions are repeated many times over the learning path, with mainly the question types varying [3]. Duolingo’s question structure also empowers the gamification process as the questions are usually short and one lesson takes about two minutes to finish. This repetition model was presented in 2016 according to the research conducted at Duolingo; see [4].

Another speaking-oriented application is Italki. It connects learners with teachers to help them learn languages through speaking [5]. Once registered, users can schedule the lessons with the teachers they prefer. It also has the “pay per lesson” approach to let learners sign up for one or two classes at the time of their convenience. Although the overall structure is similar to Kitaabi, the main difference is that Kitaabi provides classes, in other words, users select classes based on the lesson content rather than based on the teacher. This approach of Italki enforces the selection according to the teachers’ qualifications.

The usefulness of the Busuu application was also praised in several studies. The fact that the application provides learning opportunities in reading, listening, speaking, and writing attracts many learners [6]. It was also analysed that the vocabulary content of Busuu helped students learn the new words effectively. Its user-friendly interface and fun approach to language learning assisted in effective learning, see [7]. Moreover, apart from online courses, it also provides live lessons. Users can connect with the teachers through the platform and practise speaking skills. Hence, it encompasses both live lessons and online language courses.

3 Technical Architecture

3.1 Enhanced Entity-Relationship (EER) Diagram

The following points highlight key aspects of the database design based on the EER diagram:

- **User Roles and Relationships:** The **User** entity is central, supporting various roles such as **Hosts** and **Attendees**. Users can follow hosts, attend classes, and engage with language courses dynamically.
- **Course Structuring and Aggregation:** The **Course-Level Aggregation** groups courses into structured levels, ensuring a progressive learning experience. This hierarchy allows for better course management and tracking of learners’ progress.
- **Multi-Language Support:** The **Language** entity enables multilingual course offerings, linking directly to classes via the **Course-Lang** relationship. This ensures flexibility for diverse learners.
- **Flexible Hosting and Class Management:** The **Host** entity allows users with permissions to offer and manage classes, track attendees, and provide structured learning sessions. This promotes a scalable, user-driven education system.

Figure 4: Kitaabi Enhanced Entity-Relationship Diagram.

3.2 Platform Design

Kitaabi is built as a responsive web application, ensuring compatibility across devices. Key components include:

- **Frontend:** Developed with modern web technologies such as HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for an intuitive user interface.
- **Backend:** A robust Java Spring server-side system for user authentication, data management, and API services.
- **Database:** User data and application data are stored in a secure MySQL database.
- **AI Module:** Integrated with natural language processing (NLP) to power the AI Help feature.

4 AI Help The **AI Help Writing** feature leverages the **GPT-3.5** model through an **API** to provide language learners with feedback on their text. This feature enhances the learning experience by offering detailed insights into the user’s language

proficiency and areas for improvement.

Figure 5: AI Writing Help flowchart.

4.1 Workflow

1. **Text Input:** The user selects a language and enters a text minimum 30 characters.
2. **Submission:** Upon clicking the *Submit* button, the system processes the input.
3. **Prompt Generation:** The system embeds the user’s input into a predefined prompt with rules specified based on the CEFR framework [8, 3.2.1.2. Written production].
4. **API Request:** The prompt is sent to the GPT-3.5 model via the API.
5. **Response Handling:** The system receives a JSON response containing the following:
 - CEFR Level of the text.
 - Evaluation of Correctness, Clarity, and Delivery.
 - The Original Text and its Corrected Version.
 - A list of Suggestions for improvement.
6. **Feedback Display:** The feedback is showed to the user by an intuitive interface.
7. **Retry Option:** The user can modify their text and use the system again by clicking the *Try Again* button.

Overall written production

Overall written production	
C2	Can produce clear, smoothly flowing, complex texts in an appropriate and effective style and a logical structure which helps the reader identify significant points.
C1	Can produce clear, well-structured texts of complex subjects, underlining the relevant salient issues, expanding and supporting points of view at some length with subsidiary points, reasons and relevant examples, and rounding off with an appropriate conclusion. Can employ the structure and conventions of a variety of genres, varying the tone, style and register according to addressee, text type and theme.
B2	Can produce clear, detailed texts on a variety of subjects related to their field of interest, synthesising and evaluating information and arguments from a number of sources.
B1	Can produce straightforward connected texts on a range of familiar subjects within their field of interest, by linking a series of shorter discrete elements into a linear sequence.
A2	Can produce a series of simple phrases and sentences linked with simple connectors like “and”, “but” and “because”.
A1	Can give information about matters of personal relevance (e.g. likes and dislikes, family, pets) using simple words/signs and basic expressions. Can produce simple isolated phrases and sentences.
Pre-A1	Can give basic personal information (e.g. name, address, nationality), perhaps with the use of a dictionary.

Figure 6: CEFR Written Production Criteria. *Source: CEFR [3.2.1.2. Written production].*

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Kitaabi is a platform revolutionizing online language learning through innovative features and a user-friendly interface. With continuous updates and planned expansions, Kitaabi aims to become a leading name in the e-learning space.

- **Gamification for Better Learning:** We plan to integrate gamification features, including interactive challenges, rewards, and AI-driven exercises, to make the language learning process more engaging and enjoyable.
- **Integration of UzWordnet Database:** By incorporating UzWordnet [9], we aim to improve vocabulary explanations and contextual understanding. This will ensure a high level of linguistic accuracy in our language-learning platform.
- **Developing a Specialized Uzbek AI Model:** Using machine learning (ML) and natural language processing (NLP), we will train the UzWordNet dataset to develop an *advanced Uzbek AI model* tailored for language learning. Unlike general Uzbek NLP models, our approach will focus on optimizing educational applications and linguistic precision.
- **Offline Mode:** We plan to introduce an offline mode that will allow users to access lessons and practice exercises without an internet connection, making language learning more accessible.
- **Global Expansion of the Uzbek Language:** Kitaabi aims to spread the Uzbek language worldwide, making it accessible to learners across different regions. Our mission is to create a global Uzbek learning community.
- **Cultural and Traditional Lessons:** To provide a deeper understanding of Uzbek traditions and culture, we plan to introduce lessons covering history, customs, and real-life applications of the Uzbek language, with a focus beyond linguistic elements as grammar and vocabulary.

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